

Falling ball(general case) in a viscous liquid (gas)

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Let us view a falling ball in a viscous liquid(gas). First, one differential equation of the falling ball in a viscous liquid (gas) is developed. Then, a solution of this differential equation is obtained through the separation of variables. The solution is the velocity function. With integration, the depth (height) is obtained.

quantities:

m = mass of the ball
 r = radius of the ball
 v = velocity of the ball
 b = acceleration of the ball
 s = depth (height) of the ball
 φ_K = density of the ball
 φ = density of the liquid (gas)
 η = dynamic viscosity of the liquid (gas)
 c_w = drag coefficient
 t = time
 g = acceleration of free fall (due to gravity)
 λ = mean free path (gas)

$$a := 1 - \frac{\varphi}{\varphi_K}$$

$F(v)$ = resistance in a medium

a) liquids:

$$F(v) = \alpha_1 v^2 + \beta_1 v \quad (1)$$

α_1 and β_1 are functions from $r, \varphi_K, \varphi, \eta$ and c_w . With Budo [1] §92 p.525 (92.28), §94 p.535 (94.6) ,Kuchling [3] chapter 10.3.1. p.165 (M 10.20) and Timmermann [5] this formula is valid for $\frac{\varphi r v}{\eta} < 1$.

b) gas:

$$F(v) = \alpha_1 v^2 + \beta_1 v \quad (2)$$

α_1 and β_1 are functions from $r, \varphi_K, \varphi, \eta, c_w$ and λ . This is valid for $\frac{\lambda}{r} < 1$, see Budo [1] §92 p.525 between (92.28) and (92.29), see Kuchling [3] chapter 10.3.1. p.165 (M 10.20) and Timmermann [5].

equation of motion:

With Budo [1] §16 p.83 (16.3) and p.85 (16.21), it is valid:

$$m\dot{v} = mag - F(v) \cdot a \quad v(0) = 0$$

an initial-value problem

This initial-value problem can be treated through the separation of variables.

$$F(v) = \alpha_1 v^2 + \beta_1 v \quad \alpha_1, \beta_1 > 0$$

$$m\dot{v} = mag - \alpha_1 v^2 \cdot a - \beta_1 v \cdot a$$

$$\dot{v} = A - Bv - Cv^2 \quad v(0) = 0$$

with

$$A := ag \quad B := \frac{\beta_1 \cdot a}{m} \quad C := \frac{\alpha_1 \cdot a}{m} \quad B, C > 0$$

If $a = 1 - \frac{\varphi}{\varphi_K} > 0$ then $A > 0$
(motion downward)

If $a < 0$ then $A < 0$
(motion upwards)

limits of velocity:

$$0 = \dot{v} = A - Bv - Cv^2$$

$$0 = Cv^2 + Bv - A$$

$$0 = v^2 + \frac{B}{C}v - \frac{A}{C}$$

$$v_{1,2} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{A}{C} + \left(\frac{B}{2C}\right)^2} - \frac{B}{2C}$$

$$= -\frac{B}{2C} \pm \sqrt{\frac{B^2}{4C^2} + \frac{4AC}{4C^2}}$$

$$= \frac{1}{2C} \cdot \left(-B \pm \sqrt{B^2 + 4AC}\right)$$

$$v_1 = \frac{1}{2C} \cdot \left(-B + \sqrt{B^2 + 4AC}\right) > 0$$

if $A > 0$

If $A < 0$, then $v_1 < 0$.

$$v_2 = \frac{1}{2C} \left(-B - \sqrt{B^2 + 4AC} \right) < 0$$

Factoring:

$$A - Bv - Cv^2 = -C(v - v_1)(v - v_2)$$

partial fraction decomposition:

$$\frac{1}{A - Bv - Cv^2} = \frac{\alpha}{v - v_1} + \frac{\beta}{v - v_2}$$

$$1 = -C\alpha(v - v_2) - C\beta(v - v_1)$$

$$v = v_1 \Rightarrow 1 = -C\alpha(v_1 - v_2) \quad \alpha = \frac{-1}{C(v_1 - v_2)}$$

$$v = v_2 \Rightarrow 1 = -C\beta(v_2 - v_1) \quad \beta = \frac{1}{C(v_1 - v_2)}$$

it follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{v} &= \frac{1}{A - Bv - Cv^2} = \frac{-1}{C(v_1 - v_2)(v - v_1)} + \frac{1}{C(v_1 - v_2)(v - v_2)} \\ &= \frac{-1}{C(v_1 - v_2)} \left(\frac{1}{v - v_1} - \frac{1}{v - v_2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Integration: (separation of variables)

$$\begin{aligned} \int dt &= \int \frac{dv}{A - Bv - Cv^2} = \int \frac{-1}{C(v_1 - v_2)} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{v - v_1} - \frac{1}{v - v_2} \right) dv \\ &= \frac{-1}{C(v_1 - v_2)} \cdot (\ln|v - v_1| - \ln|v - v_2|) = t + d_1 \end{aligned}$$

d_1, d_2 and d are integration constants.

$$\ln|v - v_2| - \ln|v - v_1| = C(v_1 - v_2)(t + d_1)$$

$$\ln \left| \frac{v - v_2}{v - v_1} \right| = C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t + d_2$$

$$\frac{v - v_2}{v - v_1} = de^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} \tag{3}$$

$$v - v_2 = vde^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} - v_1de^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}$$

$$v \cdot \left(1 - de^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} \right) = v_2 - v_1de^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}$$

$$v = \frac{v_2 - v_1de^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}}{1 - de^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}}$$

with $v(t = 0) = 0$ and (3) we get $\frac{v_2}{v_1} = d$

$$v = \frac{v_2 - v_1 \frac{v_2}{v_1} e^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}}{1 - \frac{v_2}{v_1} e^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}}$$

$$v_2 < 0$$

$$v = \frac{v_2 \cdot (1 - e^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t})}{1 + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1} e^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}}$$

$$v = \frac{v_2 (e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} - 1)}{e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}}$$

end velocity: $v_2 < 0$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} v(t) = \frac{v_2(0 - 1)}{0 + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}} = \frac{-v_2}{|v_2|} \cdot v_1 = v_1$$

$$v_1 = \frac{1}{2C} \left(-B + \sqrt{B^2 + 4AC} \right)$$

$$v = \frac{E(e^{Ft} - 1)}{e^{Ft} + G}$$

with

$$F := -C(v_1 - v_2) \quad E := v_2 \quad G := \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}$$

$$b(t) = \dot{v}(t) = E \cdot \frac{F e^{Ft} (e^{Ft} + G) - (e^{Ft} - 1) F e^{Ft}}{(e^{Ft} + G)^2}$$

$$= E \cdot \frac{F e^{Ft} (G + 1)}{(e^{Ft} + G)^2}$$

$$= v_2 \frac{-C(v_1 - v_2) e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} \cdot \left(\frac{|v_2|}{v_1} + 1 \right)}{\left(e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1} \right)^2}$$

$$1) \quad \varphi_K > \varphi \quad \Rightarrow \quad a > 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad A > 0$$

$$v_2 < 0 \quad v_1 > 0 \quad C > 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad v_1 - v_2 > 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad -C(v_1 - v_2) < 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad v_2 \cdot (-C) \cdot (v_1 - v_2) > 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad \dot{v}(t) > 0$$

$\Rightarrow v(t)$ is a strictly increasing function.

$$2) \quad \varphi_K < \varphi \quad \Rightarrow \quad a < 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad A < 0$$

$$v_2 < 0 \quad v_1 < 0$$

$$a) \quad |v_2| > |v_1|$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad \frac{|v_2|}{v_1} + 1 < 0 \quad \text{and} \quad v_1 - v_2 > 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad -C v_2 (v_1 - v_2) \cdot \left(\frac{|v_2|}{v_1} + 1 \right) < 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \dot{v}(t) < 0$$

$\Rightarrow v(t)$ is a strictly decreasing function.

$$b) \quad |v_2| < |v_1|$$

This case doesn't occur (see formulas v_1 and v_2).

Because $v(0) = 0$, it follows $v(t) > 0$ in case 1 ($a > 0$, motion downward) and in case 2 ($a < 0$, motion upwards) $v(t) < 0$.

Integration:

$$s(t) = \int v(t) dt = \int \frac{E(e^{Ft} - 1)}{e^{Ft} + G} dt$$

see Gröbner [2] volume 1 Nr.311 p.107 2)

$$e^{Ft} = y \quad \text{thus} \quad t = \frac{1}{F} \ln y$$

$$\frac{dt}{dy} = \frac{1}{Fy} \quad y(t) = e^{Ft} \quad y(0) = 1$$

$$s(t) = \int_{y(0)}^{y(t)} \frac{E(y-1) dy}{(y+G)Fy} = \frac{E}{F} \cdot \int_{y(0)}^{y(t)} \frac{(y-1) dy}{y^2 + Gy}$$

partial fraction decomposition:

$$\frac{1}{y^2 + Gy} = \frac{\delta}{y} + \frac{\varepsilon}{y+G}$$

$$1 = \delta(y+G) + \varepsilon y = y(\delta + \varepsilon) + \delta G$$

$$1 = \delta G \quad \delta + \varepsilon = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \delta = \frac{1}{G} \quad \varepsilon = -\frac{1}{G}$$

thus:

$$\frac{1}{y^2 + Gy} = \frac{1}{Gy} - \frac{1}{G(y+G)}$$

test:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{Gy} - \frac{1}{G(y+G)} &= \frac{y+G-y}{Gy(y+G)} = \frac{G}{Gy(y+G)} \\ &= \frac{1}{y(y+G)} = \frac{1}{y^2 + Gy} \end{aligned}$$

thus:

$$\frac{F}{E} \cdot s(t) = \int_{y(0)}^{y(t)} \left(\frac{y-1}{Gy} - \frac{y-1}{G(y+G)} \right) dy$$

see Gröbner [2] Nr.12 p.7 4c):

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left[\frac{y}{G} - \frac{\ln|y|}{G} - \frac{y-1}{G} - \frac{-1 \cdot G^2 + (-1) \cdot G}{G^2} \cdot \ln|G(y+G)| \right]_{y(0)}^{y(t)} \\ &= \left[\frac{y - \ln|y|}{G} - \frac{y-1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \cdot \ln|G(y+G)| \right]_{y(0)}^{y(t)} \end{aligned}$$

test using differentiation:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{d}{dy} \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{y}{G} - \frac{\ln|y|}{G} - \frac{y-1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \ln|G(y+G)| \right) \\
&= \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{G} - \frac{1}{Gy} - \frac{1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \cdot \frac{G}{G(y+G)} \right) \\
&= \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{G} - \frac{1}{Gy} - \frac{1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G(y+G)} \right) \\
&= \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{y-1}{Gy} + \frac{-y-G+G+1}{G(y+G)} \right) \\
&= \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{y-1}{Gy} + \frac{1-y}{G(y+G)} \right) = \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{y-1}{Gy} - \frac{y-1}{G(y+G)} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

The antiderivative is confirmed.

$$y(t) = e^{Ft} \quad y(0) = 1$$

thus:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{F}{E} \cdot s(t) &= \frac{e^{Ft} - Ft}{G} - \frac{e^{Ft} - 1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \cdot \ln|G(e^{Ft} + G)| \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{G} - \frac{G+1}{G} \cdot \ln|G(1+G)| \\
&= \frac{e^{Ft} - Ft}{G} - \frac{e^{Ft} - 1}{G} - \frac{1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \ln \left| \frac{e^{Ft} + G}{1+G} \right|
\end{aligned}$$

we conclude:

$$s(t) = \frac{E}{F} \left(\frac{e^{Ft} - Ft}{G} - \frac{e^{Ft} - 1}{G} - \frac{1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \cdot \ln \left| \frac{e^{Ft} + G}{1+G} \right| \right)$$

$$s(t) = \frac{E}{GF} \left(e^{Ft} - Ft - e^{Ft} + 1 - 1 + (G+1) \cdot \ln \left| \frac{e^{Ft} + G}{1+G} \right| \right)$$

$$s(t) = \frac{E}{FG} \left((G+1) \cdot \ln \left| \frac{e^{Ft} + G}{1+G} \right| - Ft \right)$$

$$F = -C(v_1 - v_2) \quad G = \frac{|v_2|}{v_1} \quad E = v_2$$

$$s(t) = \frac{v_2 \cdot v_1}{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot |v_2|} \cdot \left(\left(\frac{|v_2|}{v_1} + 1 \right) \cdot \ln \left| \frac{e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}}{1 + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}} \right| + C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t \right)$$

$$v_2 < 0$$

$$= \frac{v_1}{C(v_1 - v_2)} \cdot \left(\left(\frac{|v_2|}{v_1} + 1 \right) \cdot \ln \left| \frac{e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}}{1 + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}} \right| + C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t \right)$$

thus $s(t=0) = 0$

s must not be too large, because of the pressure (gas) and the density (liquid). The free fall in air with pressure change is treated at Shea [4].

References

- [1] Budo, A: Theoretische Mechanik 10.edition (1980) Deutscher Verlag der Wissenschaften
- [2] Gröbner, W and Hofreiter, N: Integraltafel 1.Teil 5.edition (1975) Springer Verlag Wien
- [3] Kuchling, H: Taschenbuch der Physik (1979) Verlag Harri Deutsch Frankfurt am Main
- [4] P.Mohazzabi, J.H.Shea: High-altitude free fall, Am.J.Phys. 64 (10) p.1242-1246 (1996)
- [5] P.Timmermann, J. van der Wee: On the rise and fall of a ball with linear or quadratic drag, Am.J.Phys. 67 (6), June 1999 p.538-546